

This is the authors' version (post peer-review) of the manuscript:

T Pucher et al Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics, 58(18), 185102

<https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6463/adc273>

That has been published in final form at:

<https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1361-6463/adc273>

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2 **Short-wave infrared photocurrent spectroscopy to probe narrow-gap 2D** 3 **materials**

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11 **ABSTRACT**

12 The capability of characterizing low-bandgap two-dimensional (2D) materials is crucial for
13 a wide range of applications from fundamental science to commercial implementation.
14 Current techniques rely heavily on expensive characterization equipment and thus hinder
15 focused research on low-bandgap materials, compared to their counterparts in the visible
16 range of the electromagnetic spectrum. This work demonstrates a cost-efficient and easily
17 rebuildable optical setup to probe low-bandgap 2D materials using photocurrent
18 spectroscopy. The heart of the setup consists of a supercontinuum laser in combination with
19 a diffraction grating to create a tunable light source working from 500 to 2000 nm, allowing
20 to access bandgaps in the short-wave infrared, far from what is possible using standard silicon
21 detector technology. Apart from a complete technical guide to facilitate reproduction of the
22 system, two popular narrow-gap materials (MoTe₂ and black phosphorus) have been studied
23 to extract bandgaps and excitonic features of these materials. The results highlight the simple,
24 yet powerful approach of utilizing photocurrent spectroscopy in the infrared and thus
25 expanding the analysis toolbox for narrow-gap 2D semiconductor research.

1 INTRODUCTION

2 Since the isolation of single-layer MoS₂ by mechanical exfoliation the field of two-
3 dimensional (2D) semiconductors has kept blooming. Sulfur- and selenium-based transition
4 metal dichalcogenides have attracted much of the attention and most of the efforts have been
5 focused on studying this family of 2D semiconductors¹⁻³. One of the reasons for this success
6 might be that their emission/absorption occurs in the visible or near-infrared (NIR) part of
7 the light spectrum where many affordable characterization and spectroscopy tools are
8 available. As a result, these materials have been integrated in a wide range of optoelectronic
9 applications, such as photodetectors, lasers or modulators⁴⁻⁸. Although narrower bandgap 2D
10 semiconductors, such as MoTe₂, black phosphorus (BP) or PtSe₂, showed potential in the
11 same research fields⁹⁻¹³, they have been less studied. However, it is important to note that
12 semiconductors with emission/absorption occurring in the short-wave infrared (SWIR) part
13 of the spectrum are essential for many relevant technologies, such as photonics-based
14 computing, telecommunications and thermal imaging¹⁴⁻²². Whereas conventional
15 semiconductors for infrared applications are difficult to implement with current silicon
16 technology^{23,24}, their 2D material counterparts are benefiting from their integration
17 compatibility and versatility with a wide range of systems, including CMOS²⁵⁻³⁰.
18 Additionally, van der Waals materials as opposed to bulk materials allow multi-material
19 combinations of choice, due to the lack of lattice matching concerns³¹⁻³³. Thus, it is important
20 to develop affordable experimental tools that could allow to broaden the community of
21 researchers pushing forward the science of 2D narrow gap semiconductors.

22 Angle-resolved photoemission spectroscopy (ARPES) is used to extract information about
23 band structure, density of states (DOS) or bandgap³⁴⁻³⁶, specifically suited for narrow gap

1 semiconductors. However, its widespread application is hindered by technical challenges and
2 intrinsic limitations, such as the need for ultrahigh vacuum conditions, and the difficulty in
3 probing states above the Fermi level. Optical spectroscopy techniques, on the other hand,
4 provide a very affordable alternative to probe band gaps in semiconductors.
5 Photoluminescence (PL), for example, can be used to identify excitonic features, doping or
6 defect effects³⁷⁻⁴⁰. Transmission and reflectance spectroscopy⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ as well as ellipsometry⁴⁵⁻
7 ⁴⁷ are commonly applied to study optical properties of 2D materials, such as optical
8 conductivity or complex reflective indices. However, most of these widespread optical
9 spectroscopy techniques rely on silicon photodetector technology, which is limited to the
10 NIR range. Probing 2D materials in the SWIR mainly relies on high-cost Fourier transform
11 infrared (FTIR) spectrometers, often in combination with other expensive equipment, such
12 as liquid nitrogen-cooled detectors⁴⁸⁻⁵¹.

13 The purpose of this work is to demonstrate the potential of photocurrent spectroscopy using
14 a tunable light source, operating in the 500-2000 nm wavelength range, to probe the optical
15 properties of 2D semiconductors with bandgaps narrower than 1.1 eV, which therefore
16 cannot be easily characterized with most widespread reflectance/absorbance or
17 photoluminescence setups that rely on silicon photodetector technology. Photocurrent
18 spectroscopy provides a facile, yet powerful approach to study excitonic features in 2D
19 materials⁵². Up to now, photocurrent spectroscopy has been used to resolve spectral features
20 in transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) within the visible and NIR part of the
21 electromagnetic spectrum⁵³⁻⁵⁵ and to resolve dark magnetic excitons of 2D semiconductors⁵⁶,
22 but as of our knowledge, it has not been demonstrated as a reliable method to probe the
23 optical properties of narrow gap 2D semiconductors.

1 **METHODS**

2 **2D material exfoliation and transfer**

3 MoTe₂ and black phosphorus flakes were obtained from bulk crystals (α -MoTe₂ HQ
4 Graphene, BP Smart Elements) by mechanical exfoliation using Nitto tape (Nitto SPV 224)
5 onto a PDMS substrate (Gel-Film WF 4 × 6.0 mil by Gel-Pack). After flake selection and
6 identification with an optical microscope⁴³ the flakes were directly transferred⁵⁷ from the
7 PDMS to the final substrate.

8 **Electrode Deposition**

9 Prepatterned gold electrodes were fabricated by evaporation of 5 nm Ti (used as adhesion
10 layer) and 45 nm Au onto a SiO₂ (285 nm)/Si (p++) substrate through a shadow mask (Ossila,
11 E321) in an electron-beam evaporator system.

12 **Electrical characterization**

13 All optoelectronic characterizations of the devices were carried out in a home-built vacuum
14 chamber. A source-meter unit (Keithley 2450) was used for performing the electrical
15 measurements between source and drain electrodes. Two TENMA programmable benchtop
16 power supplies (model 72–2715) are connected in series to apply gate voltages.

17

18 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

19 We start by describing our self-assembled tunable light source setup. The system is based on
20 a supercontinuum laser (YSL SC-PRO) and a home-made monochromator. Figure 1a shows
21 a scheme of the system. Briefly, the supercontinuum laser output provides a collimated beam
22 that is shined onto a diffractive reflective grating (Thorlabs GR13-0305), mounted onto a

1 rotator stage (Thorlabs ELL8K/M). The corresponding reflected beam is scattered by the
 2 grating (see Figure 1b) and the first order diffracted light is aligned with a collimator that
 3 “couples” the output light into a multimode fiber. It’s important to note that we use the finite
 4 diameter of the multimode fiber (here, 400 μm) as an aperture pinhole to spatially select part
 5 of the scattered spectrum without the need for an external slit. Our system uses a mechanical
 6 shutter before the free-space to multimode fiber coupling to facilitate illumination chopping
 7 in synchrony with the rotator steps, which could be achieved with an external chopper disc
 8 as well. The fiber allows to connect the rotator system to any external measurement setup. In
 9 our case the laser beam is guided into a zoom lens system ensuring that the surface of the
 10 fiber end is placed at the image plane of the zoom lens system, resulting in an optical
 11 projection of the fiber core onto the sample surface. This method provides a circular light
 12 spot with uniform power density on the device, avoiding the typical Gaussian-shape spots.

14 **FIG.1: Optical setup illustration of the tunable light system.** (a) 3D schematic of the setup,
 15 depicting two main setup components. The laser light from a supercontinuum laser is fed into the
 16 rotator stage using a collimator. The rotator stage consists of a diffraction grating mounted onto a
 17 rotator, enabling to select the first order of the input beam and couple it into a multimode (MM) fiber.
 18 The fiber consequently guides the light to the lens tube stage, which is where the sample is placed.
 19 High-pass (HP) filters allow to prevent unwanted diffraction orders to hit the sample and a 50/50
 20 beamsplitter (BS) enables simultaneous light power measurement. (b) Illustration of the diffraction
 21 orders after the grating. A sheet of paper is used to highlight the different orders of light, in particular
 22 highlighted are the direct reflection (0^{th} order) and the first order of the laser beam. The first order is
 23 subsequently coupled into the MM fiber. The light path is highlighted by green dashed arrows.

1

2 Including a filter holder at the output of the zoom lens makes it possible to reject higher
3 diffraction orders by placing high-pass filters a different wavelength scanning ranges. We
4 also use a 50:50 beamsplitter that separates the light beam right before it hits the sample,
5 allowing to simultaneously measure light power using a power meter. A complete table of
6 all used parts can be found in the Supporting Information.

7 Figure 2a shows some examples of spectra of the output light obtained while rotating the
8 grating, with one set of data taken in the visible range (average FWHM = 12.6 nm, using a
9 Si-based spectrometer) and another set taken in the SWIR range of the spectrum (average
10 FWHM = 27.3 nm, using an InGaAs-based spectrometer). The output wavelength can be
11 continuously tuned by rotating the grating. Figure 2b shows the extracted relationship
12 between the position of the rotator stage (equipped with a sensor) and the output light
13 wavelength. To select a specific wavelength from the supercontinuum output of the light
14 source, we use a diffraction grating, that separates the different wavelengths of the light.
15 More specifically, in our case that is a blazed refractive grating, as these particular kinds of
16 gratings are designed to maximize the output of one of the orders and minimizing losses to
17 the other output orders. In this case it is the first order, which can also be seen in Figure 1b
18 as the spot of the highest light intensity. The geometry and working principle of a blazed
19 grating is depicted in the inset of Figure 2b. In contrast to other diffraction gratings, the
20 blazed grating has a direction defined by the blaze arrow. When the input light beam is hitting
21 the grating, its wavelengths get separated according to the incident (Θ_i), blaze (β) and
22 reflection (Θ_m) angle, defined by the grating geometry and following the grating equation

23 $d \cdot \sin(-2\beta) = m\lambda,$ (1)

1 where d is the separation of the blaze and m is an integer that represents the output order.

2 It is worth mentioning, that we found the calibration can be done in the whole operation range

3 of 500 to 2000 nm even without using an infrared (IR) spectrometer. One can effectively use

4 higher order diffractions to measure the output of the tunable light source in the IR using an

5 inexpensive silicon-based spectrometer. The Supporting Information Figure S2 shows a

6 comparison of spectra acquired with the InGaAs spectrometer with those obtained with the

7 Silicon spectrometer after multiplying their wavelength values by their “ n^{th} ” diffraction order

8 number. Figure 2c shows the wavelength-dependent optical power of our system, measured

9 with Silicon (500-1100 nm) and Germanium (700-1800 nm) photodiodes (Thorlabs PM100D

10 coupled with Thorlabs S120C and S122C, respectively). The peak in output power at a

11 wavelength of ~ 1100 nm stems from the pumping wavelength of the supercontinuum laser.

12

13

14 **FIG.2: Output characteristics of the setup.** (a) Convolved output spectra for different wavelengths

15 ranging from the visible to the SWIR light spectrum. (b) Rotator angle vs. wavelength for the whole

16 operation range. The rotator angle corresponds to the input beam angle on the grating, which is related

17 to the n^{th} order output by the type of grating (inset). (c) Output light power vs. wavelength without

18 the use of a beamsplitter. The peak in output power around 1110 nm is related to the pump frequency

19 of the supercontinuum laser.

20

1 In the following, we illustrate the potential of the system in combination with photocurrent
2 spectroscopy with two archetypical narrow gap 2D semiconductors: MoTe₂ and black
3 phosphorus (BP). The materials are mechanically exfoliated and transferred onto a
4 viscoelastic stamp (details in the methods section). The stamp surface is inspected under an
5 optical microscope and flakes are selected according to their opacity. Selected flakes are then
6 dry transferred⁵⁷ onto a SiO₂/Si substrate with pre-patterned Ti/Au electrodes. Due to their
7 reduced environmental stability in contrast to other 2D materials the devices were placed
8 inside a miniature homemade high-vacuum chamber right after transfer and subjected to a
9 thermal annealing step under high-vacuum conditions.⁵⁸

10 The photocurrent spectra are acquired by setting the rotator/grating to a given angle, therefore
11 selecting a laser output wavelength, and measuring a current vs. time trace while keeping the
12 device at a constant source-drain bias, while the shutter is cycled from closed to open to
13 closed (with a time of 10s for each state). A wavelength-dependent photocurrent trace is
14 acquired by repeating this process for different rotator angles, hence changing the grating
15 angle relative to the input beam and controlling the light output with the shutter. It is
16 important to note that each time the shutter lets light pass onto the sample, the integrated
17 beamsplitter allows us to measure light power simultaneously and that the wavelength sweep
18 is paused at 700 nm and 1200 nm to insert high-pass filters (Thorlabs 650 & 1000 FELH
19 filters), to avoid illumination contribution originating from higher diffraction orders. The
20 responsivity can be obtained by dividing the measured photocurrent by the light power
21 reaching the channel area. Figure 3c and 3d show the resulting responsivity vs. wavelength
22 for MoTe₂ and black phosphorus, respectively. The spectra display excitonic features at the
23 expected wavelengths when compared with studies doing photoluminescence or absorbance

1 within the SWIR range for these materials, as discussed with more detail in the following.
2 Several peaks, related to transitions in distinct parts of the Brillouin zone, can be clearly
3 assigned to the spectrum of MoTe₂ (Figure 3c), that have been confirmed by other works.^{59–}
4 ⁶¹ A (1.09 eV) and B (1.35 eV) peaks are associated with the direct excitonic transitions at
5 the K-point, whereas the C peak (2.4 eV) is related to parallel band regions at the Γ -point.^{62–}
6 ⁶⁴

7 Due to BP's optical anisotropy, the absorption is known to change with the polarization
8 direction of the incoming light, having maximum absorption with incident light polarized in
9 the armchair (AC) direction.^{49,65–67} The supercontinuum source produces unpolarized light
10 and we did not change the polarization state for these experiments. BP's layer-dependent
11 optical transitions have been studied extensively using FTIR spectroscopy in those previous
12 works. The most prominent peak, which we also observe in our photocurrent spectroscopy
13 measurements (Figure 3d) is related to the direct optical transition between the highest
14 valence band (v_1) and the lowest conduction band (c_1) at the Γ -point of the Brillouin zone,
15 thus getting commonly labeled as E_{11} (ground state exciton transition). Interestingly, using
16 our system we are able to not only see the ground state transition but also its excited state
17 ($2s$), which shows up as a weaker peak next to the E_{11} transition and has been identified in
18 other works, but is not resolved easily.⁶⁸ To better visualize the occurring peaks we have
19 performed a fit using pseudo-Voigt functions, which are commonly applied to fit excitonic
20 features in 2D materials.^{69–71} To fit the responsivity spectrum of BP with low error we need
21 three pseudo-Voigt functions (depicted in Figure 3d). Detailed information on the individual
22 fit functions, background and overall fit can be found in the supporting information (Figure
23 S4). Two of the pseudo-Voigt functions are corresponding to the already described E_{11} and

1 2s transition, while the third transition at an energy of 0.91 eV (labelled with *) can be
 2 attributed to hybrid dark transitions in few-layer BP, as assigned previously.⁴⁹ The band
 3 structure of BP is affected by the applied electric field and hybrid transitions reportedly shift
 4 to lower energies with increasing electric field strength.⁷² The excited state transition (2s) is
 5 even more visible when the photo responsivity data is presented as a Tauc plot of BP's direct
 6 bandgap (see Figure 3f).

7

8

9 **FIG.3: Probing narrow band gap material devices.** (a) Sketch of device connections and
 10 configuration. The device is annealed and subsequently measured inside a miniature vacuum chamber
 11 equipped with a window to enable sample illumination. (b) Close-up image of the miniature vacuum
 12 chamber with a connected device. Two pins are establishing source-drain connection and the bottom
 13 Si substrate is used as gate and connected via conductive silver paint. The scale bar is 10 mm. (c) and
 14 (e) Photocurrent spectroscopy results of probing a few-layer MoTe₂ device. (c) Wavelength-
 15 dependent photo-responsivity of the MoTe₂ device, clearly highlighting the different excitonic
 16 transitions, characteristic for MoTe₂. The inset demonstrates part of the measured current vs. time
 17 curve for the wavelengths 1130 & 1140 nm. (e) Tauc plot of the responsivity curve from (c) for
 18 indirect transition and a linear fit for bandgap determination, resulting in an approximated bandgap
 19 of 0.87 eV. (d) and (f) Photocurrent spectroscopy results of probing a few-layer black phosphorus
 20 device. (d) Wavelength-dependent photo-responsivity of the black phosphorus device, featuring the

1 characteristic, including fitted pseudo-Voigt functions to visualize the E_{11} transition, the 2s transition
2 and a hybrid transition (*). The final fit is depicted as a black dash-dotted line, which follows the
3 experimental data with low error. (f) Tauc plot of the responsivity curve for the direct band transition,
4 giving a band gap of 0.68 eV.

5
6 We can further analyze the band edge of the materials by re-plotting the lower-energy part
7 of the spectra following a Tauc plot representation, assuming an indirect bandgap for
8 MoTe_2 ^{73,74} and a direct bandgap for black phosphorus. A linear extrapolation and the crossing
9 with the horizontal axis allow to estimate the absorption band edge for the two materials at
10 0.87 eV and 0.68 eV respectively. These values are in line with previous experimental
11 measurements. The band edge for few-layer MoTe_2 has been determined in the range of 0.85-
12 0.9 eV.^{61,75} By comparing the calculated band edge for BP with layer-dependent absorbance
13 measurements from other works, we confirm that our BP device has a layer thickness of
14 4L.^{66,68} By analyzing the transmission of the BP flake on PDMS prior to transfer, we are
15 obtaining transmission values for the blue and green channel (97% and 98%, respectively)
16 that support the obtained layer number (Supporting information Figure S5).⁷⁶

18 CONCLUSION

19 In summary, we have established, built and characterized a monochromator-based setup, to
20 study narrow-gap 2D semiconductors using SWIR photocurrent spectroscopy. Our system is
21 capable of wavelength-selective tuning in the range of 500-2000 nm. We give full
22 information of assembly details, including an entire parts list for replication purposes.
23 Additionally, we have proven the capability of our system to work with 2D materials by
24 probing two different narrow-bandgap materials, namely MoTe_2 and black phosphorus.

1 These two materials are perfect examples for demonstrating the system's ability to exemplify
2 optical features, such as exciton transitions and bandgaps in the SWIR. By visualizing the
3 excitonic features of few-layer MoTe₂ and BP and determining their optical band edges, we
4 demonstrated that photocurrent spectroscopy in the infrared is a powerful tool which enables
5 to shed light on the rich many-body physics found in 2D materials with low bandgaps, not
6 easily accessible by standard means.

7

1

2 **DATA AVAILIBLITY**

3 The data of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

4

5 **COMPETING INTERESTS**

6 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

7 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

8 We acknowledge funding from the EU FLAG-ERA project To2Dox (JTC-2019-009) and the
9 Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (Grants PID2020-115566RB-I00, TED2021-
10 132267B-I00, CEX2018-000805-M-19-2 and PDC2023-145920-I00). This work was
11 supported by the Open Fund of State Key Laboratory of Infrared Physics (Grant No.SITP-
12 NLIST-ZD-2024-01).

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32

Supporting Information

Short-wave infrared photocurrent spectroscopy to probe narrow gap 2D materials

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FIG.S1: Detailed setup images. (a) Setup overview with the supercontinuum laser on the left connected to the rotator stage with a collimator. After the input beam is diffracted by the grating the light is collected and further propagated through the multimode (MM) fiber, which can be connected to the measurement stage. (b) Detailed image of the rotator stage without lid. The blazed grating is mounted on a rotation stage. The light enters on the right-hand side of the box, hits the grating and the diffracted beam gets collected by a collimator on the bottom part of the picture, which connects to the MM fiber. A detailed part list can be seen on Table S1.

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4 **FIG.S2: Infrared range output comparison by second order multiplication.** Plotted is the output
 5 of multiple states of our tunable system above a wavelength of 1000 nm measured in two distinct
 6 ways. First, the output is measured using an IR spectrometer (blue dashed line) and secondly the
 7 output is measured with a normal spectrometer in the range of 500-900 nm and subsequently
 8 multiplied by a factor of 2. The comparison shows that the system's whole range of wavelengths
 9 (500-2000 nm) can be determined without the need for an IR spectrometer.

10

11

12 **FIG.S3: MoTe₂ device characteristics.** (a) Transfer curve of the few-layer MoTe₂ device under a
 13 source-drain bias of 1 V. The inset shows a microscope image of the contacted flake. (b) Response
 14 time of the device under a pulse with a wavelength of 1140 nm (highlighted in Figure 3b of the main
 15 text). Rise time is around 100 ms.

1

2

3 **FIG.S4: BP responsivity fit functions.** Three pseudo-Voigt functions and a background function are
4 used to fit the responsivity spectrum of the black phosphorus device. The experimental data can be
5 fitted with low error.

6

1

2 **FIG.S5: BP transmission channels.** (a) Exfoliated black phosphorus flake on PDMS before dry-
 3 transfer. The thin 4L part of BP is highlighted as dashed black line and the transmission line profile
 4 cut is highlighted as dotted red line. The scale bar is 10 μm . (b) The device with the BP flake
 5 transferred between gold electrodes. The scale bar is 10 μm . (c) Blue transmission channel line profile
 6 extracted from (a) using Gwyddion software. The transmission is 97% in respect to the PDMS
 7 substrate. (d) Green transmission channel line profile extracted from (a) using Gwyddion software.
 8 The transmission is 98% in respect to the PDMS substrate.

9

10

Item	Specification	Provider	Price (EUR)
Rotation Stage	ELL8K/M	Thorlabs	276.76
Grating clamp	CH1A	Thorlabs	65.34
Breadboard small	MB1015/M	Thorlabs	44.47
Breadboard big	MB3030/M	Thorlabs	156.73
Post 1	P150/M	Thorlabs	55.08
Post base	PB4/M	Thorlabs	13.71
Clamping Fork 1	PF175	Thorlabs	16.63
V-Clamp	C1513/M	Thorlabs	272.12
Clamping Fork 2	CF125C/M	Thorlabs	11.66
Pedestal Post Holder (4x)	PH30E/M	Thorlabs	99.32
Clamping Fork 3	CF038	Thorlabs	40.51
Post 2 (4x)	TR30/M	Thorlabs	19.56
Post 3	TR50/M	Thorlabs	5.36
Post holder	UPH75/M	Thorlabs	33.76
XY stage SM1	LM1XY/M	Thorlabs	133.62
SM1 to SM05 adapter	SM1A6	Thorlabs	20.74
Collimator package	F220SMA-780	Thorlabs	164.53
M11 to SM05 adapter	AD1109F	Thorlabs	32.67
Grating	GR13-0305	Thorlabs	71.00
Clamp	PM4/M	Thorlabs	24.30
Cardboard 1	TB5	Thorlabs	58.18
Cardboard 2	TB4	Thorlabs	69.11
Laser Safety Screen (2x)	TPS4	Thorlabs	85.32
Masking tape	T743-1.0	Thorlabs	23.16
Shutter with controller	SHB1T	Thorlabs	991.26
Multimode Fiber	M45L01	Thorlabs	80.88
Beam Block	LB2/M	Thorlabs	164.13
			3029.91

1

2 **TABLE S1: System parts list.** All links last accessed on October 14, 2024. The supercontinuum
3 laser used was a YSL SC-PRO.

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